

Performing Intent-based data operation in the computing continuum: the INTEND project

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ABSTRACT

The European Commission (EC) Digital Decade strategy to gain by 2030 autonomy in the digital economy requires more and more data to be processed in the Cloud-Edge-IoT computing continuum, instead of only in the central cloud. This requires advanced automation and intelligence of the continuum. The European Union (EU)-funded project INTEND aims at bringing human-like intelligence into the cognitive continuum, to achieve the novel concept of intent-based data operation. The outputs pave the way of migrating EU's data industry from cloud to the continuum, and implement EC's strategy of human-centric AI in the domain of data processing.

1 PROJECT'S DESCRIPTION

Processing large amounts of data creates immeasurable value for Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML)-based applications [1] but also generates huge cost, with much of the cost concentrated to the few public cloud providers [3]. The Digital

decade policy program of the European Commission (EC), aiming at reaching an EU digital autonomy by 2030, pushes to exploit resources at the edge of the telecommunication network for data processing, to reduce the cost and the dependency to central cloud providers [6]. More and more EU organizations should have their data pipelines running in the computing continuum instead of the central cloud, but this requires advanced automation and intelligence of the continuum [4], since doing so at the edge is much more complicated than in the cloud.

The EC has recently funded 9 projects under the call HORIZON-CL4-2023-DATA-01-04 for applying AI to achieve cognitive computing continuum, with promising outcomes towards high-level automation [2]. However, at the same time, many people worry that AI lacks sufficient intelligence to do creative work, e.g., in the context of the continuum, to use the heterogeneous and unconventional devices in unpredicted ways, to handle resources at different places from different providers in a strategic way, and to understand what the human stakeholders really need. Despite a

Figure 1: Components of the intent-based human-AI interaction. Pillar 3 is shown in green.

decade of effort on improving automation, central cloud vendors still offer human service representatives to their large customers.

In the meantime, recent breakthroughs in AI research have shown human-like intelligence in the direction of generative AI [9], neural-symbolic AI [8], and deep reinforcement learning [5]. Such unprecedented intelligence has the potential to disrupt how people use the cloud-edge computing continuum.

The INTEND project. This paper presents the INTEND research project¹ towards cognitive computing continuum with advanced intelligence to achieve the novel *intent-based data operation*. By exploiting these latest AI breakthroughs, it is possible to bring the next-level human-like intelligence into the *cognitive* computing continuum, allowing the latter to adapt, think and talk like humans: continually learn how to adapt data pipelines to heterogeneous and unconventional resources in an effective way, make strategic decisions at different places in the continuum like the human brain thinks in a multi-objective way, and chat with human stakeholders in natural language to understand their intents and explain what was done. INTEND “Intent-based data operation in the computing continuum” is a Horizon Europe research project funded by the EU. It started in January 2024 and is expected to last 36 months.

Partners. SINTEF AS (Norway) is the project leader. The project involves both academic and industry partners. Academic partners are Sapienza Università di Roma (Italy), Technische Universität Wien (Austria), GATE Institute Sofia University (Bulgary), Seoul National University (Korea) and Hanyang University (Korea). The industry partners provide coverage of the complete supply chain of compute continuum, from chips (Intel Deutschland GmbH, AiM Future), servers (Dell Technologies), cloud infrastructure (Ericsson), telecom (Telenor ASA), software (CS-Group), conversational AI (Onlim GmbH) to consultancy (NEXTWORKS).

Goals and contribution. INTEND’s research will lead to 11 novel software tools for the cognitive continuum, with a focus on intelligent operation of data pipelines, organized in three main research pillars, each corresponding to a specific objective, as illustrated in Figure 1 with Pillar 3 shown more in detail. The key idea behind Pillar 3 is to use Knowledge Graphs to provide a machine-readable representation of intents, and a novel code-switching approach to connect the common KG with decision makers. Between the KG and stakeholders, the natural language interface extracts stakeholders’ intents from direct dialogs or existing artifacts, and explains to

the stakeholders how and why the AI models made certain adaptations based on the existing intents. Tools in Pillar 2 will handle the distributed and dynamic nature of computing continuum by decentralized and federated decision coordination, to combine the adaptation decisions made by different AI models. Finally, tools in Pillar 1 will handle the hardware diversity by continual learning, i.e., to learn autonomously what is the best way to use the resources in the continuum based on observing how the data pipelines perform. We now discuss pillars/objectives and related tools.

- **Objective/Pillar 1.** Achieve intelligent management of computing, storage, network, and neural processing resources based on continual learning, to better exploit diverse and unconventional hardware on edge and cloud. Expected output consists of 4 tools: **inStore**, intelligent data placement and storage management in cloud and edge, the Kubernetes² based **inOrch** [7] tool for hardware-aware intelligent orchestration of data processing services, the **inNet** for AI-powered intent-based networking, and the **inNeural** tool for intelligent adaptation of concurrent multimodal workloads on AI accelerators.
- **Objective/Pillar 2.** Enable strategic and federated decision making covering multiple AIs from different perspectives and places across the continuum, to achieve end-to-end data security and sustainability. Expected output consists of 3 tools: **inCoord**, a decentralized and federated decision coordinator for global adaptation, the **inSustain** tool to comprehensively measure the sustainability of data pipelines, and **inSec** to assess end-to-end data security on multi-provider security and identity management mechanisms.
- **Objective/Pillar 3.** Achieve human-centric data operation, via a novel natural language interface for data stakeholders to efficiently express their data operation intents, and understand and trust the AI-made decisions. Expected output consists of 4 tools: the **inGraph** tool, to manage the intent knowledge graph for cognitive data operation, **inSwitch** to perform code-switching between intent knowledge graph and decision-making contexts, **inGen** to extract intents and generate decision-making explanations, and **inChat**, a chat-based interface for continual interaction.

We will validate INTEND platform in five vertical use cases on Video streaming, Machine data, 5G data infrastructure, Urban dataspace and Robotic AI. All use cases demand advanced data operation from different perspectives, involving stakeholders like data engineers, AI researchers and non-IT consultants.

Relevance for the KDD ecosystem. The INTEND project directly aligns with the following topics in the KDD call for paper.

- “Data Science – Methods for analyzing graphs”. The INTEND platform is based on Knowledge Graph patterns to interpret the user intent.
- “Big Data – parallel and distributed data science (cloud)”. Data stakeholders will be able to chat about how they intend their data pipelines to perform in the continuum.
- “Foundations – AI and interpretability”. INTEND will use continual reinforcement learning to orchestrate data

¹<https://intendproject.eu>

²<https://kubernetes.io/>

pipelines. Furthermore, it will explain to the stakeholders what it is planning to do, for safer data operation.

2 DEMO SCENARIO

The project is at the end of the requirement definition phase, focusing on designing starting features of tools, identifying techniques, AI models, datasets and interaction between tools. The initial demo consists of state-of-the-practice data operation, showing demands of intent-based data operation on sample scenarios and running “on the paper”. One sample scenario is inspired by the *Machine data* use case, lead by Fill GmbH, an international special machinery and plant engineering company. Fill’s CYBERNETICS ANALYZE is the data analytics platform that Fill provides to their customers, i.e., factories. Our demo will improve how data pipelines are operated in such data platform based on intents expressed by salespeople (who have more business than IT background), e.g. what new data analytics components are needed to meet the customers’ requirements, e.g. what is the required data quality and latency and what is the expected energy consumption. Afterwards, the demo will generate Docker commands to automatically adjust the pipeline orchestrations and the resources according to these intents.

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